

Membrane assisted reactive distillation for bioethanol purification

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Abstract

Reactive distillation and membrane assisted reactive distillation have been considered as possible alternatives to extractive distillation for the concentration of ethanol from diluted streams. Aquaporin-based biomimetic forward osmosis membranes have been tested for ethanol tolerance and ethanol rejection. The experimental results were used to construct the process simulations developed by Aspen Plus. Different alternatives were proposed where the pre-concentration step was performed by membrane stand alone or a combination of membrane and ordinary distillation. In all the configurations reactive distillation using ethylene oxide was considered to reach the ethanol final concentration of 99.9 wt%. Ethanol recovery, the energy consumed per kg of ethanol produced, the total annual cost and economic analysis were used to compare the alternatives. It was obtained that ordinary distillation coupled with reactive distillation is at the moment the only alternative competing with extractive distillation. However, the sequence of membrane, ordinary distillation and reactive distillation has clear potentials to compete with the distillation stand-alone processes once that solutions for draw recovery and minimization of ethanol lost will be available.

Keywords: Reactive distillation, forward osmosis, membrane separation, bioethanol

1. Introduction

The Sustainable Development Scenario (SDS) was introduced in the World Energy Outlook 2017 to offer “an integrated way to achieve a range of energy-related goals crucial for sustainable economic development: climate stabilization, cleaner air and universal access to modern energy, while also reducing energy security risks”.¹ The SDS defines a set of desired outcomes and the actions required to deliver them. In particular, in 2040 low-carbon sources are expected to contribute by 40% in the energy mix. Nevertheless, the global biofuel production is not increasing quickly enough to meet the SDS demands. Biofuel production grew 7% year-on-year in 2018 to reach 152 billion litres, but average production growth of 3% per year is anticipated over the next five years. This is below the sustained annual growth of 10% until 2030 required to comply with the SDS.² Research efforts are still required to reduce biofuels production costs along all the process line, from feedstock selection and treatment to product recovery and separation.

According to Renewable Fuels Association,³ the world production of bioethanol was 108 million cubic meters in 2018, bringing bioethanol to the highest step of the podium as the main biofuel used in the world.⁴ Bioethanol has a long history, from the late 1800s when Henry Ford and Nicholas Otto build engines that could run on ethanol, an outstanding research effort allowed bioethanol production to overcome ethical issues, create new jobs and displace imported crude oil.

Research on new raw materials for bioethanol conversion represents undoubtedly the more discussed topic in the literature. Additionally, also the bioethanol purification step keeps attracting the interest of the scientific community in order to reduce its energy demand. Two main challenges can be highlighted in the optimization of the separation process. The first is related to the feed composition which is a diluted aqueous solution of ethanol coming from the fermentation step. The second is related to the presence of a minimum azeotrope between water and ethanol that limits the purity achievable in unit operations based on liquid-vapor equilibria.

Different separation techniques have been proposed and evaluated during the years:

1. Extractive distillation. In extractive distillation a solvent is added to cause an increase of the relative volatility of the key components to the extent that separation becomes feasible and economical.⁵ This technology was extensively studied for the separation of ethanol-water water mixtures in order to define new configurations^{6,7} or testing alternative solvents.⁸
2. Heterogeneous distillation. In heterogeneous distillation an entrainer that forms a heterogeneous azeotrope with one or more components in the feed is used. The entrainer is concentrated in the overhead vapor and when condensed forms a second liquid phase that is

recirculated as reflux. The other liquid phase and the bottom streams are the products.⁹ Together with extractive distillation these are the preferred options for large scale bioethanol production. Different works focused in the optimization of the process or in defining intensified alternatives.^{10,11}

3. Pressure-swing distillation. Pressure-swing could be advantageous when the binary azeotrope disappears or changes composition by 5% or more over a moderate range of pressure. In this case the separation can be performed in two ordinary distillation columns operating at different pressures.⁵ Differently from the previous cases, pressure swing distillation does not require a mass separation agent. Furthermore, the difference in pressure between the columns opens different possibilities for heat integration.^{12,13}
4. Reactive distillation (RD). The azeotrope can be circumvented in systems where the distillation is combined with a reaction. The simultaneous reaction and separation allow overcoming of azeotropic concentrations and distillation boundaries facilitating the products purification.¹⁴ When applied to ethanol-water separation, different alternatives have been proposed. Among all, Lu et al.¹⁵ proposed a reactive distillation process where water is eliminated by reaction with isobutene, while Guzman-Martinez et al.¹⁶ considered propylene oxide and ethylene oxide. An et al.¹⁷ choose the hydration reaction of ethylene oxide to overstep the azeotrope. This reaction alternative was recently reconsidered by Kaymak.¹⁸ RD for separation of ethanol from aqueous solutions should not be confused with RD used for the synthesis of ethanol. This case can be revised in the study of Cardenas-Guerra et al.¹⁹ where ethanol was produced by reaction of ethylene and water.
5. Adsorption. For azeotropic separations, adsorption is used to selectively adsorb one component in a fixed-bed adsorbent. Different works have been published for the ethanol-water separation testing different adsorbent materials to bring this separation to a potential industrial application.²⁰ A review of different adsorbents, process parameters, kinetic and mathematical models have been discussed by Karimi et al.²¹
6. Membrane separation. Membranes can be defined as a thin interface that moderates the permeation of chemical species in contact with it.²² Because the separation is not limited by the relative volatility, separation by membrane, is claimed to be economically more convenient compared to distillation when azeotropic mixtures are considered.^{23,24} In bioethanol production, membranes can be integrated in different sections of the process as reviewed by Wei et al.²⁵ and Lipnizki.²⁶

7. Hybrid systems. Hybrid flowsheets are obtained combining different unit operations to overcome their individual limitations.²⁷ Fuel grade ethanol was obtained by liquid-liquid assisted extractive distillation in a study of Aviles Martinez et al.²⁸ The liquid-liquid extraction was performed with n-dodecane to remove most of the water, then the ethanol purity required was reached in an extractive distillation column using glycerol as entrainer. The combination of membranes and ordinary distillation was considered by Skiborowski et al.²⁹ In their work they consider a distillation column to approach the ethanol-water azeotropic composition and a pervaporation step to further purify the ethanol. Different hybrid systems for ethanol dehydration were reviewed by Roth et al.³⁰

Since membranes and reactive distillation are emerging as the most promising techniques to achieve savings in both energy and capital costs, in the present study a hybrid process that combines these unit operations is considered. Ethanol is a molecule that can easily permeate through polyamide-based membranes such as reverse osmosis³¹ leading to the de-alcoholization of feeds.³² Additionally, it has previously reported that ethanol can cause swelling in polymeric membranes,³³ potentially provoking changes in the membrane structure that could ultimately affect the global process performances negatively. For this reason, in this study aquaporin-based biomimetic forward osmosis membranes were chosen to preconcentrate the diluted ethanol-water stream before being fed to the reactive distillation column where the reaction between water and ethylene oxide is carried out.

Aquaporins are water channels that allow the pass of water rejecting all other impurities.³⁴ Aquaporin-based forward osmosis membranes have previously proved to be suitable for the dewatering of fermentation broths.³⁵ Therefore, pre-concentration of ethanol using aquaporin-based forward osmosis membranes before reactive distillation could enhance the overall process performance. Different process configurations have been compared to the classic extractive distillation process using the total annual cost, the ethanol recovery and the energy index as confront criteria.

This study:

- Reports novel experimental data of aquaporin-based forward osmosis membranes stability and rejection data for concentration of ethanol model solutions
- Studies the performance of the reactive distillation column including the by-products purification
- Presents an economic analysis of the alternatives considered.

2. Materials and methods

Forward osmosis (FO) was chosen as a technique for the ethanol-water separation. Hollow fibers membrane modules (HFFO2) have been used for the experiments. The module consists of a biomimetic hollow fiber element comprising a layer of polyamide thin film composite. The active layer is coated with aquaporin proteins on the lumen side of the fibers. The fibers have an inner diameter of 0.195 mm and a length of 300 mm. The module has a diameter of 70 mm and the overall membrane area is 2.3 m².

All the experiments and the modeling of the different alternatives were done considering a hypothetical fermentation broth containing 5 wt% ethanol. This value is aligned with different works where actual fermentation broths were considered.³⁶⁻³⁸ Ethanol with a minimum purity of 99.9 wt% is the production requirement.

2.1 Ethanol exposure tests

In order to verify the membrane stability to a progressively more concentrated ethanol solution, quality control (QC) tests were performed before and after the ethanol exposure. To be within the QC-standards, aquaporin membranes must meet the following requirement:

1. Water flux (J_w) from the feed to the draw side, higher than 15 L m⁻² h⁻¹
2. Reverse salt flux (J_s) from the draw solution to the feed lower than 2.5-3 g m⁻² h⁻¹
3. Specific reverse salt flux (J_s/J_w), the ratio between the reverse salt flux and the water flux lower than 0.2 g L⁻¹

The exposure experiments were run in batch mode for 24 hours. Aquaporin membranes were exposed to ethanol solutions of 5, 10 and 25 wt% in the feed side keeping the draw side empty and open. These pre-selected ethanol concentrations simulate the increasing ethanol concentration during the forward osmosis concentrating process. After the exposure the membranes were rinsed with water and the QC-tests performed. Ethanol 99.5 vol% (VWR, USA) was used.

The experimental setup used for the exposure tests can be seen in the supporting material.

2.2 Ethanol rejection tests

Once the membrane stability was confirmed through during the ethanol exposure tests previously described, the ethanol rejection tests were performed. The single-pass set-up used for the experiments is reported in Figure 1. The trans-membrane pressure was adjusted by the valve and kept at 0.2 bar. Samples of feed inlet and feed concentrate are taken from the dedicated sample

valves, and samples of the draw outlet are taken from the outlet stream. The process recovery, defined as the amount of feed removed in the draw, was calculated from the feed (Q_f) and the permeate flowrate (Q_p) according to Equation 1:

$$\text{Process recovery} = \left(1 - \frac{Q_p}{Q_f}\right) \% \quad (1)$$

During the experiments the recovery was kept constant adjusting the feed and draw flow rated. Tests were performed at 30, 50 and 80% recovery.

Figure 1. Flow sheet of the single-pass set-up.

The experiments were run for 60 minutes and samples were collected at 15, 30, 45 and 60 minutes. In order to evaluate the separation performances, the rejection percentage (R) was introduced. The rejection indicates the amount of ethanol retained by the membrane and it is defined according to Equation 2.

$$R = \left(1 - \frac{C_p}{C_{av}}\right) \quad (2)$$

where C_p is the ethanol concentration in the permeate and C_{av} is the arithmetic average between the concentration of ethanol in the feed inlet and in the feed concentrate.

The draw solution was a 4.17 M solution of NaCl.

2.3 Process modeling

The process alternatives considered are summarized in Figure 2. The base case, used as benchmark to evaluate the performances of the alternatives proposed, is the extractive distillation sequence reported in Figure 2(a). This configuration was proposed by Errico et al.⁶ after screening different configurations with different number of columns and different recycle set-ups. It is composed by three columns; in the first one called pre-concentrator (PC), the fermentation broth is upgraded to a concentration near the azeotropic one, in the second column, pure ethanol is recovered as distillate

by using ethylene glycol (EG) as entrainer. The third column is used for solvent recovery and the distillate, composed by water and traces of ethanol, is recycled to the PC. Figure 2(b) reports the first alternative obtained as a combination of an ordinary distillation (PC) and RD. The design of the reactive distillation column is based on the hydration reaction between ethylene oxide (EO) and water to produce ethylene glycol (EG). The water is consumed by the reaction and pure ethanol can be recovered as distillate. In Figure 2(c) the PC was substituted by aquaporin forward osmosis (FO) membranes. In the last option, reported in Figure 2(d) the pre-concentration step was distributed between FO and PC.

Figure 2. Base case, extractive distillation (a), PC plus RD sequence (b), FO plus RD (c). FO plus PC plus RD (d)

All the flowsheets considered were modeled by means of the process simulator Aspen Plus V11. For the distillation columns, the rigorous method RadFrac was used. The NRTL thermodynamic method was chosen to describe the system deviations from the ideality. Pressure drops and stage efficiencies were not considered in the design. All the columns were considered equipped with sieve trays 0.6 m spaced. A bottom liquid sump and a top vapor disengagement of 2.5 and 1.25 m respectively were also considered. To each column is associated a floating head kettle reboiler and a

fixed tube condenser. The membrane unit was not simulated in Aspen Plus since what is relevant for the calculation is the composition of the concentrate stream that was experimentally evaluated. The process performances were evaluated through the evaluation of three indexes: the total annual cost (TAC), the ethanol recovery (ER) and the energy index (EI).

The total annual cost (TAC) is obtained as the sum of the annualized capital costs and the operative costs due to the steam used in the columns reboilers, the cooling water in the condensers and the solvents or reactants. Aspen Economic Analyzer was used to evaluate the TAC considering an operational time of 10 years and 8000 hr yr⁻¹. The capital cost of the membranes was considered equal to 110 \$ m⁻² with an average volume discount of 15% based on information provided by the vendor. Maintenance was not included in the economic evaluation.

The ethanol recovery is defined as the ration of the molar flow rate of the component in the stream where it is recovered and in the fermentation broth.

The energy index is obtained as the ratio between the total reboiler duty of the configuration and the total flow rate of ethanol produced.

The ER and EI are evaluated based on the solution of the material and energy balances provided by Aspen Plus.

3. Process alternatives results

3.1 Case 1: Base case process – extractive distillation

According to Errico et al.⁶ 32,907 kg/h of a mixture of 5 wt% ethanol was fed to the first column at 1 atm as saturated liquid. All the columns operate at atmospheric pressure. The TAC was evaluated equal to 332 k\$ yr⁻¹. Of this cost, 140 k\$ yr⁻¹ are due to the annualized capital costs.

The ER and the EI for the base case extractive distillation are equal to 98.6 % and 6.86 MJ kg⁻¹ respectively.

Details of the energy and mass balances for the base case configuration are available in the supporting material.

3.2 Case 2: Ordinary distillation preconcentration plus reactive distillation

In the design of this alternative reported in Figure 2 (b), the parameters for the PC were obtained from the previous case and it is discussed here the design procedure followed for the RD.

As first step it is necessary to define the kinetic scheme.

The reaction scheme chosen in this work is based on the two reactions reported in Equations 3 and 4.

The same reaction scheme was used by Ciric and Gu,³⁹ and Al-Arfaj and Luyben⁴⁰ using the kinetic parameters reported by Altiokka and Akyalcin.⁴¹

This scheme represents an improvement with respect to the works of Tavan and Hosseini⁴² and Keymak¹⁸ where only the main reaction (Equation 3) had been considered. However, the presence of side products can affect the purity of the EG produced and consequently the process layout to achieve a purity that matches the market requirements. The reaction parameters used are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Rate constants for the reactions reported in Equations 3-4

Reaction	Reaction rate [$kmol m^{-3}s^{-1}$]
3	$3.15 \cdot 10^{12} \exp(-9547/T)x_{EO}x_{H_2O}$
4	$6.30 \cdot 10^{12} \exp(-9547/T)x_{EO}x_{EG}$

In order to design the reactive distillation, different parameters need to be defined and optimized. The column pressure, the reactant and distillate flow rate, the reflux ratio, the location of the feeds, the stage hold up, and the extend of the reactive zone, are going to be discussed independently in the following subsections.

3.2.1 Column pressure

The operative pressure is one of the most important parameters for the reactive distillation column. The change in the pressure affects the temperature profile, the corresponding reaction rates, and relative volatilities impacting both the kinetics and the separation. For the system considered, different values of the pressure have been reported in the literature. Tavan and Hosseini⁴² select 101.3 kPa as operative pressure without exploring its variation on the column performances. A more complete analysis was done by An et al.¹⁷ where the water conversion, the EO conversion, the ethanol recovery and the EG selectivity were explored in the pressure range 200-1000 kPa. They select 600 kPa as optimal value based on the conversion of water and EO and the high EG selectivity. Kaymak¹⁸ explored the range 101.3-607.9 kPa and the value of 456 kPa was chosen as optimal based on the reactant conversion. The highest value was considered by Okasinski and

Doherty.⁴³ They defined 1520 kPa as the pressure necessary to assure a temperature of 200°C in the reactive zone of the column.

All the cited works based the optimization of the pressure on indexes related to the reaction conversion and the amount of product obtainable. However, the decomposition temperature of EG is also a constrain for the selection of its optimal value. According to Beach⁴⁴ EG degrades very slowly at temperature lower than 163°C. This temperature was widely exceeded in the design reported by Kaymak¹⁸ since the EG recovered as bottom stream in the reactive column had a temperature of 254.78°C. The same consideration applies for the design reported by Al-Arfaj and Luyben⁴⁰ where the bottom temperature was 300°C. Nevertheless, depending on the pressure and the flow rate of EO, the bottom stream could be more or less concentrated in DEG. The DEG has a decomposition temperature above 200°C⁴⁵ allowing an extension of the pressure range admissible. Using the initial design parameters reported in the supplementary material, the effect of the column pressure was explored in the range of 100-1500 kPa. To these extremes correspond a bottom temperature of 91 and 224°C, respectively. The influence of the pressure on the ethanol purity, the ethanol recovery and the reboiler duty are reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Variation of the ethanol purity, recovery, and reboiler duty with column pressure.

3.2.2 Effect of the EO/water ratio

Based on the reaction reported in Equation 3, on molar basis, the ratio between EO and water should be at least 1. A higher amount benefits the purity and recovery of ethanol to the detriment of the EG production. Considering the main production goal is the ethanol separation, the purity of the bottom stream becomes of secondary importance.

Figure 4 reports the influence of the EO/water molar ratio on the ethanol purity, recovery and reboiler duty.

Figure 4. Influence of the EO/water ration on ethanol purity, recovery and reboiler duty

In the neighborhood of a ratio of 1.5 it is possible to reach high ethanol purities with a recovery higher than 95%. This value agrees with the analysis reported by An et al.¹⁷

3.2.3 Effect of distillate flow rate and reflux ratio

The distillate flow rate is expected to equal the amount of ethanol in the feed. A lower value penalizes the purity and the recovery due to increase of ethanol in the bottom stream. This behavior was depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Influence of the distillate flowrate on ethanol purity, recovery and reboiler duty

More interesting is the influence of the reflux ratio. As expected, its increase corresponds to a linear increase in the reboiler duty, but differently from ordinary columns, this is not completely true for the ethanol purity and recovery as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Influence of reflux ratio on ethanol purity, recovery and reboiler duty

This behavior may be due to the presence of multiple steady states.^{46,47}

3.2.4 Effect of feed locations

The effect of the EO and azeotropic feed location have been reported in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Effect of feed stage location EO (left), azeotropic feed (right), on ethanol purity, recovery and reboiler duty

Differently from An et al.¹⁷ it was chosen to keep the feed separated. From Figure 7 (left) it is possible to notice that after the 6th stage the location of EO does not influence the column performance. This was expected since if the EO is the lightest compound, if fed too close to the top it could easily reach the condenser. The azeotropic feed from the preconcentration column has its optimal location after the 25th stage, where the maximum ethanol purity and recovery is observed.

3.2.5 Effect of the liquid hold-up

The hold-up affects directly the net reaction rate. As it can be seen from Figure 8, its increase corresponds to an improvement of the purity and a decrease of the reboiler duty. It should be kept in

mind that an increase of the hold-up requires a higher column diameter. The choice of the hold-up was constrained to the maximum liquid height of 12 cm on the reactive stages.

Figure 8. Effect of the total liquid hold up on the ethanol purity, recovery, and reboiler duty

3.2.6 Optimization procedure

The column pressure, the ratio EO/water, the distillate flowrate, the reflux ratio, the feed location and the liquid hold up were optimized in a sequential way. Starting from the initial design the influence of the pressure was examined first, checking its influence on the product purity and respecting the constrains of the products decomposition temperature. The optimal value selected was used to evaluate the effect of the EO/water ratio. The optimal value selected was used to repeat the pressure optimization. In this way the new optimized variable was used to check its influence on the previous variables. Once that all the variables were optimized the influence of the number of reactive stages, and the rectifying and stripping stages was considered. The optimized design is reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Configuration parameters and selected outputs for the optimized reactive distillation design

Variable	
EO [kmol/h]	10.28
Distillate [kmol/h]	34.43
Bottom stream [kmol/h]	33.05
Reflux ratio	0.96
Pressure [kPa]	2100
Number rectifying stages	1
Number reactive stages	23
Number stripping stages	11
EO feed stage	24
Azeotropic feed stage	27
Stage hold up [L]	156.52

Distillate ethanol mass fraction	0.9999
Column diameter [m]	1.41
Reboiler duty [kW]	511.46
Reboiler temperature [°C]	150.30
Condensed duty [kW]	705.21

Based on the optimization results, the bottom stream of the reactive distillation column is composed mainly of DEG (85 mol%), a minor part of EG (0.30 mol%) and the rest equally distributed between water and ethanol. In order to valorize this stream producing pure DEG with a market value, a new configuration was proposed according to Figure 9. A new ordinary distillation column was added to purify the DEG obtained from the RD, at the same time the ethanol and water recovered as distillate are sent back to the pre-fractionator to increase the ethanol recovery. This configuration achieved a TAC of 371 k\$ yr⁻¹, 165 of those are due to the annualized capital costs. Moreover, an ER of 98.6 % and an EI of 7.10 MJ kg⁻¹ was evaluated.

Figure 9. Modified PC plus RD configuration for DEG purification

The stream summary for this configuration is reported in the supplementary material.

3.3 Case 3: Membrane assisted reactive distillation

The membrane is now considered in a hybrid configuration to substitute the ordinary distillation preconcentration step according to the flowsheet reported in Figure 2(c).

The membrane stability was tested first according to the methodology reported in Section 2.1. The QC-test results before and after exposure to solutions with increasing concentration of ethanol are depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10. QC results for membrane exposure to 5, 10 and 25 wt% ethanol solutions

Based on the QC results it is possible to assure that the membrane performances were not affected when being exposed to increasing concentration of ethanol.

Following the methodology described in Section 2.2, the results for the water flux and the ethanol rejection were summarized in Figure 11 for the different recoveries examined.

Figure 11. Ethanol rejection (left), water flux (right) vs operating time at 30%, 50%, and 80% permeate recoveries

From Figure 11 it is evident that the highest ethanol rejection and water flux are obtained for 80% recovery. Moreover, their values are constant over the time. The flowrates of feed inlet, concentrate, draw inlet and outlet corresponding to each recovery examined are provided as supplementary material.

In order to evaluate the overall performance of the membrane within the ethanol dehydration plant it is important to quantify how much ethanol is recovered in the feed solution and how much ethanol is lost in the draw solution since this affects the final amount of ethanol sellable. The concentration of ethanol in the feed concentrate (C_c) and draw outlet (C_{do}) is reported in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Ethanol concentration in the feed concentrate stream (left) and in the draw outlet (right)

The choice of which recovery needs to be used can not be done based only of the concentration values. Examining the ration between the feed flow rate and the draw flow rate reported in Figure 13, it is possible to notice that to achieve a recovery of 80% it is required a draw flow rate comparable to the feed flowrate, which implies a high consumption of draw solution. This value is halved when 50% of feed recovery is considered. The draw flow rate also affects the amount of ethanol lost. In particular, when 80% recovery is considered, about 30% of the ethanol of the feed is lost in the diluted draw solution. The loss was quantified in about 15% when the recovery was set to 50%.

Figure 13. Ethanol rejection vs feed inlet to draw inlet flow rate ration for different recoveries

Based on this consideration, 50% recovery was chosen as setting for the preconcentration step.

Based on the experimental results obtained for aquaporin-based forward osmosis membranes, the optimization of the RD was repeated for the new pre-concentrated feed composition. In this case the RD operates with a high amount of water in the feed since the membrane configuration used does not reach the azeotropic composition. This requires the column to operate with a higher amount of EO. The membrane area necessary for the separation was evaluated in 2558 m². Analogously to the RD of Figure 9, if also the DEG separation column is considered, this alternative reaches a TAC of 1544 k\$ yr⁻¹, an ER of 83.9 % and an EI of 32.32 MJ kg⁻¹. Due to its high energy consumption, the configuration of membrane assisted reactive distillation as a stand-alone pre-concentration step is not further considered. However, the flowsheet, the design parameters and the stream summary are provided as supplementary material.

3.4 Case 4: Membrane assisted ordinary distillation and reactive distillation

Another possibility to integrate FO into the separation sequence is to use the membrane to reduce the duty of the pre-concentration column. Including also the DEG separation column, the separation sequence become: membrane – pre-fractionator – reactive distillation – DEG recovery. In this way the configuration initially envisaged in Figure 2(d) was updated and reported in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Modified FO plus PC plus RD configuration for DEG purification

Main simulation results for this case are summarized in Table 3 and 4.

This sequence is able to reach a 26% reduction of the pre-concentrator reboiler duty and an the overall reboiler consumption of 2486.66 kW that corresponds to a 23% reduction compared to the total reboiler duty of the reactive distillation sequence of Fig. 9 and 20% reduction compared to the base case extractive distillation sequence of Fig. 2(a). The configuration achieved a TAC of 284 k\$ yr⁻¹, an ER of 87.2 % together with a remarkable EI of 6.16 MJ kg⁻¹. The annualized capital costs contributed for 44% of the TAC.

Table 3. Stream summary for the configuration reported in Figure 14

Variable	Stream			
	Ethanol	DEG	Water, Ethanol	Concentrate
Flowrate [kmol/hr]	31.2	4.78	0.72	864.18
Temperature [K]	371.20	517.51	412.71	364.88
Vapor fraction	0	0	1	0
Composition [mole fraction]				
Ethanol	0.9990	Trace	0.0921	0.0364
Water	0.0010	Trace	0.8899	0.9636
EO	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	
EG	0.0000	0.001	0.0018	
DEG	0.0000	0.9990	0.0162	

Table 4. Design parameter, condenser and reboiler duties for the configuration of Figure 14

	Column
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Variable	1	2	3
Number of stages	27	37	12
Feed stage:			
Concentrate	18	---	---
Water, Ethanol	24	---	---
EO	---	24	---
Az. feed	---	27	---
DEG, By-products	---	---	
Distillate [kmol/hr]	36.7	31.2	0.72
Reflux ratio	3.48	0.96	0.34
Reboiled duty [kW]	1982.5	472.16	32.00
Condenser duty [kW]	1085.4	639.14	5.08

4. Economic analysis

The comparison of the alternatives considered can not be based only on the analysis of the TAC, ER, and EI. In fact, while the reference case is based on extractive distillation using ethylene glycol as entrainer, in the RD based alternatives it is necessary to take into account the cost of the EO and the value of the DEG produced. Moreover, in hybrid alternatives with membranes it is necessary to take into account the cost of the draw solution. Since the different alternatives have a different ER and consequently a different ethanol production, the corresponding total annual sales revenue needs to be estimated. Considering an average ethanol price of 1.05 \$ L⁻¹,⁴⁸ 74 \$ kmol⁻¹ for the EO,⁴⁹ 117 \$ kmol⁻¹ for DEG,⁵⁰ 84 \$ kmol⁻¹ for the ethylene glycol,⁷ and 42 \$ ton⁻¹ for the NaCl, the results for the different alternatives were summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Economic comparison of the alternatives considered

Alternative	Ethanol revenue [k\$ yr ⁻¹]	DEG Revenue [k\$ yr ⁻¹]	EG cost [k\$ yr ⁻¹]	EO cost [k\$ yr ⁻¹]	Draw cost [k\$ yr ⁻¹]	Utility cost [k\$ yr ⁻¹]	Annualized capital cost [k\$ yr ⁻¹]	Profit [k\$ yr ⁻¹]
<i>Case 1 – Fig. 2(a)</i>	18,590	---	672	---	---	192	140	17,586
<i>Case 2 – Fig. 9</i>	19,275	4802	---	6092	---	206	165	17,614
<i>Case 4 – Fig. 14</i>	17,050	4474	---	5671	865	159	125	14,704

5. Conclusions

The possibility to concentrate ethanol diluted stream by membrane assisted reactive distillation have been considered proposing different configurations. The results have been compared with the same

separation performed by extractive distillation with ethylene glycol as a solvent. Aquaporin-based forward osmosis membranes were tested, and the performances used to set the Aspen simulations. The reactive distillation unit, based on the reaction with ethylene oxide and water, was optimized considering all the main design parameters and highlighting as the choice of the pressure is also related to the decomposition temperature of the bottom stream. Despite the lowest value of the TAC and the energy index indicated in the configuration reported in Figure 14, based on the sequence forward osmosis membrane – pre-fractionator – reactive distillation – DEG recovery by ordinary distillation (Case 4), as the best alternative, a deeper economic analysis showed a different scenario. This configuration is in fact penalized by a lower recovery due to the loss of ethanol in the draw solution and to the cost of the draw solution. However, the low energy consumption and capital investment should drive more efforts in optimizing the membrane separation stage in order to limit the ethanol loss in the draw solution and also in defining solutions to recycle the draw solution. The reactive distillation alternative coupled with pre-concentration by distillation and DEG recovery (Case 2) appears to be an interesting alternative to extractive distillation realizing the highest profit. An et al.¹⁷ simulated the same system in a reactive distillation reporting an EI equal to 5.32 MJ kg⁻¹ that is lower than 7.10 MJ kg⁻¹ obtained in the present work. However, considering that An et al.¹⁷ did not consider the pre-concentration step. Recalculating the EI for the design proposed without considering the pre-concentration step the corresponding value is 1.28 MJ kg⁻¹ representing a big improvement in terms of energy consumption.

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